

COGNITIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING: BENEFITS AND FUNCTIONS

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Abstract: The article discusses and defines the cognitive learning and explains how we can use it to improve our performance at work and in other aspects of life. Human brain can absorb and store information through experiences, sensations, and thoughts through a process called cognition. Unleash our brain's full potential through an active learning style known as cognitive learning. Its purpose is to make it easy to link new information with existing ideas. Cognitive learning helps you master your career by highlighting the best ways to learn.

Key words: Cognitive learning, brain's full potential, improve comprehension, explicit learning, meaningful, active independence.

Introduction

Cognitive learning theory views second language acquisition as a conscious, rational thought process that involves the conscious use of learning strategies. A learning strategy is a special kind of information processing that improves comprehension, learning, or retention of information. This description of language learning is in stark contrast to behaviorist descriptions of language learning, which view language learning as an unconscious, automatic process. Cognitive learning is a learning style that focuses on using the brain more effectively. Cognition is the mental process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through sensations, experiences, and thoughts. Once we master the basics of cognitive learning, it becomes easier to maintain a lifelong habit of continuous learning.

Functions of cognitive learning

Cognitive learning is an immersive, active process that puts the senses to work in constructive and long-term ways. Instead of emphasizing rote memorization like traditional classroom learning methods, cognitive learning focuses on past knowledge. Not only does this make cognitive learning a more effective way to acquire knowledge, but it also makes you a better learner in the long run.

Here are some examples of cognitive learning:

1. Implicit learning

Learning happens implicitly when there is no active intention to acquire knowledge. It's a form of random, automatic learning because you're unaware of the process, but later you realize you're holding onto the information.

Examples of this learning are talking, walking, eating, and other things you learn without conscious thinking. For example, you can learn to type without looking at the keyboard.

2. Explicit learning

When a person consciously seeks knowledge, they learn explicitly. That includes trying to learn new skills and processes that are essential for their job or going back to school to learn more.

Unlike implicit learning, which comes naturally, explicit learning requires conscious action and sustained attention to acquiring new knowledge. Cognitive learning helps us learn more

clearly by giving you great insight into the subject matter and how it relates to our current and future work. For example, when we enroll in a PowerPoint class to improve our presentation skills.

3. Meaningful learning

Meaningful learning occurs when people relate new knowledge to past information and experiences. It includes emotional, motivational, and cognitive aspects and helps deepen knowledge and problem-solving skills. For example, taking an advanced management course to become a better team leader and gaining a deeper understanding of previous leadership training.

4. Collaborative learning

Engage in collaborative learning when learning new processes as a group or team at work. Collaborative learning helps deepen collaboration and bring out the best skills of all participants in your event. This cognitive learning has her four components:

- Simultaneous interaction
- active interdependence
- personal responsibility
- equal participation

Similarly, collaborative learning is a cognitive strategy in which a resource person teaches a group how to develop ideas about a particular skill or knowledge area. For example, your company can train colleagues on new production processes so that they can pass on their knowledge to her members of the team.

5. Discovery learning

When we actively seek new knowledge, we learn through discovery. If one enjoys exploring new concepts and processes, delving deeper into topics outside their main area of expertise, and applying new information to their work, they are practicing discovery learning. For example, they can learn about new workflow apps that are gaining popularity in the industry.

6. Associative learning (habituation and sensitization)

Non-associative learning is divided into his two styles of habituation and awareness. Both focus on how to learn based on responses to continuous stimuli.

Habituation is learning from habit. This is the decreased response to stimuli after prolonged exposure. For example, once you get used to it, you won't notice the noise when working in a factory. Over time, I've learned to ignore the stimulus, so the sound doesn't bother me.

The opposite of habituation is sensitization. This is because repeated exposure to a stimulus increases the response. For example, you may be more sensitive to ringing landlines. Both types of learning are basic and can be adapted to different life and work situations.

7. Emotional learning

This cognitive strategy helps people learn emotional intelligence and other aspects of controlling their emotions and understanding the emotions of others. Whether you're a leader or a junior, emotional intelligence plays an important role in empathy, interpersonal relationships, and effective communication. For example, emotional learning helps maintain warm relationships with both introverted and extroverted colleagues, regardless of their position within the organization. Mastering this learning will improve your relationships at work and in your personal life.

8. Hands-on learning

People often learn best through experience. Experiential learning is a cognitive strategy that enables us to glean valuable life lessons from our interactions with other people. However, experience is subjective and subject to interpretation. For example, medical interns can gain insight into patient care, diagnosis, empathy, and compassion by accompanying experienced physicians. This allows two people to have the same experience and learn different lessons from the event. The value of your experience depends on your level of introspection and reflection and how you relate it to past events.

9. Receptive learning

This is a form of receptive learning if one likes to learn through a lecture where a person stands up and talks about a topic while the audience listens and takes notes. It is passive for learners as it involves active participation. Participation in taking notes and asking questions is limited. For example, when an organization invites an expert to train a team in a classroom or workshop.

10. Observational learning

This cognitive learning strategy involves imitation. Imitation is an effective learning tool, especially for children. Adults, however, can imitate others and learn the skills and traits they desire. He can learn leadership skills by emulating a leader in his field. You can also become a better team his player by practicing good team his player habits. For example, observing managers who are good at long-term planning can improve their strategic thinking skills.

Conclusion

Cognitive learning is a great way to master a profession. It helps you optimize the use of your brain, thoughts, emotions, and experiences. Cognitive strategies condense learning activities into fully immersive events that build on past information and apply to future scenarios. If you want to be an effective learner who enjoys the quest for knowledge for a lifetime, practice the cognitive learning strategies above to excel at work and in any field.

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